

**D-JRP7-1.2 first panel of
strains available to sequence**

JRP7 - LISTADAPT

V1 15/06/2018

Responsible Partner: ANSES

GENERAL INFORMATION

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Description of the panel of strains to be sequenced

1. Strains from Veterinary Research Institute

Number of strain	Date de rélevement	Country	Region	Lokality	Source	Serotype	Code ListAdapt
L 2695	20/03/2010	Czech Republic	South-Moravian Region	Brno - Jundrov	mud with decaying vegetation - bank of Svratka river	1/2a	CZ-NAT-SO-9
L 2705	28/03/2010	Czech Republic	South-Moravian Region	Brno - Marijánské valley	decaying leaves near a river	1/2a	CZ-NAT-SO-10
L 2707	11/04/2010	Czech Republic	South-Moravian Region	Brno	soil before a stable (horses)	1/2a	CZ-NAT-SO-11
L 2748	02/05/2010	Czech Republic	South-Moravian Region	Věstonice - Nove mlýny	water vegetation (algae) from the bank of pond	1/2a	CZ-NAT-VE-12
L 2749	02/05/2010	Czech Republic	South-Moravian Region	Pasohlávky - Nové mlýny	decaying vegetation from the bank of Jihlava river	1/2a	CZ-NAT-VE-13
L 2750	28/04/2010	Czech Republic	South-Moravian Region	Heršpice	mud from river	1/2a	CZ-NAT-SO-14
L 2778	13/05/2010	Czech Republic	South-Moravian Region	Nové Dvory	soil - fence with pigs	1/2a	CZ-NAT-SO-15
L 2806	11/07/2010	Czech Republic	South-Moravian Region	Brno - Game reserve Holedná	mud from pond	4b	CZ-NAT-SO-16
L 2808	11/07/2010	Czech Republic	South-Moravian Region	Brno - Game reserve Holedná	soil near the feeding rack	4b	CZ-NAT-SO-17
L 2809	11/07/2010	Czech Republic	South-Moravian Region	Brno - Game reserve Holedná	mud	1/2a	CZ-NAT-SO-18
LV 751	23/07/2016	Slovak Republic	Banskobystrcký Region	Německá	mud- bank of river (river inflow Hron)	1/2a	CZ-NAT-SO-19
LV 752	24/07/2016	Slovak Republic	Banskobystrcký Region	Budča	mud- bank of river (river inflow Hron)	1/2a	CZ-NAT-SO-20
LV 753	24/07/2016	Czech Republic	South-Moravian Region	Brno - Game reserve Holedná	mud from pond	4b	CZ-NAT-SO-21
LV 756	14/08/2016	Czech Republic	Zlín Region	Velehrad	mud from pond	4b	CZ-NAT-SO-22
LV 757	14/08/2016	Czech Republic	Zlín Region	Velehrad	mud from pond	1/2a	CZ-NAT-SO-23
LV 760	14/08/2016	Czech Republic	Zlín Region	Velehrad	water from pond	1/2a	CZ-NAT-WA-24
LV 771	28/08/2016	Czech Republic	Olomouc Region	Týn nad Bečvou	mud-bank of pond	1/2a	CZ-NAT-SO-25
LV 852	05/10/2016	Czech Republic	South-Moravian Region	Pouzďřany	mud - Svratka river	1/2a	CZ-NAT-SO-26

LV 854	05/10/2016	Czech Republic	South-Moravian Region	Iváň	mud-bank of pond	1/2a	CZ-NAT-SO-27
LV 903	28/10/2016	Czech Republic	Vysočina Region	Panenská Rozsírka	mud - rive spring-Dyje	1/2a	CZ-NAT-SO-28
LV 925	05/11/2016	Czech Republic	Vysočina Region	Třešť	decaying vegetation - Valcha pond	1/2a	CZ-NAT-VE-29
LV 926	05/11/2016	Czech Republic	Vysočina Region	Třešť	decaying vegetation - Valcha pond	1/2a	CZ-NAT-VE-30
LV 962	19/11/2016	Czech Republic	Vysočina Region	Třešť	mud - river	1/2b	CZ-NAT-SO-31
LV 964	19/11/2016	Czech Republic	Vysočina Region	Třešť	mud - river	1/2a	CZ-NAT-SO-32
LV 965	19/11/2016	Czech Republic	Vysočina Region	Třešť	vegetation - bank of river	4b	CZ-NAT-VE-33
LV 966	19/11/2016	Czech Republic	Vysočina Region	Třešť	vegetation - bank of river	1/2a	CZ-NAT-VE-34
LV 968	19/11/2016	Czech Republic	Vysočina Region	Třešť	moss + soil, bank of pond	1/2a	CZ-NAT-SO-35
LV 1011	15/04/2017	Czech Republic	South-Bohemian Region	Kunžak	moss + soil, bank of pond	1/2a	CZ-NAT-SO-36
LV 1039	03/08/2017	Czech Republic	South-Bohemian Region	Jindřichův Hradec	mud from pond	1/2a	CZ-NAT-SO-37
LV 1048	10/09/2017	Czech Republic	South-Moravian Region	Ždárec	mud from pond	1/2a	CZ-NAT-SO-38

2. Strains from Norwegian veterinary institute

strain ID	Geographic information	year*	type of animal	MLST data	Listadapt_ID
VI 58121	Norway-gardens and grass fields	2012	slugs (<i>A. vulgaris</i>)	ST220	NO-OTH-O-1
VI 58123	Norway-gardens and grass fields	2012	slugs (<i>A. vulgaris</i>)	ST759	NO-OTH-O-2
VI 58125	Norway-gardens and grass fields	2012	slugs (<i>A. vulgaris</i>)	ST398	NO-OTH-O-3
VI 58127	Norway-gardens and grass fields	2012	slugs (<i>A. vulgaris</i>)	ST6	NO-OTH-O-4
VI 58128	Norway-gardens and grass fields	2012	slugs (<i>A. vulgaris</i>)	ST37	NO-OTH-O-5
VI 58129	Norway-gardens and grass fields	2012	slugs (<i>A. vulgaris</i>)	ST1	NO-OTH-O-6
VI 58130	Norway-gardens and grass fields	2012	slugs (<i>A. vulgaris</i>)	ST6	NO-OTH-O-7
VI 58132	Norway-gardens and grass fields	2012	slugs (<i>A. vulgaris</i>)	ST18	NO-OTH-O-8
VI 58133	Norway-gardens and grass fields	2012	slugs (<i>A. vulgaris</i>)	ST124	NO-OTH-O-9
VI 58135	Norway-gardens and grass fields	2012	slugs (<i>A. vulgaris</i>)	ST1	NO-OTH-O-10
VI 58136	Norway-gardens and grass fields	2012	slugs (<i>A. vulgaris</i>)	ST91	NO-OTH-O-11
VI 58137	Norway-gardens and grass fields	2012	slugs (<i>A. vulgaris</i>)	ST399	NO-OTH-O-12
VI 58138	Norway-gardens and grass fields	2012	slugs (<i>A. vulgaris</i>)	ST4	NO-OTH-O-13
VI 58139	Norway-gardens and grass fields	2012	slugs (<i>A. vulgaris</i>)	ST1	NO-OTH-O-14
VI 58140	Norway-gardens and grass fields	2012	slugs (<i>A. vulgaris</i>)	ST1	NO-OTH-O-15
VI 58141	Norway-gardens and grass fields	2012	slugs (<i>A. vulgaris</i>)	ST19	NO-OTH-O-16
VI 58143	Norway-gardens and grass fields	2012	slugs (<i>A. vulgaris</i>)	ST219	NO-OTH-O-17
VI 58145	Norway-gardens and grass fields	2012	slugs (<i>A. vulgaris</i>)	ST91	NO-OTH-O-18
VI 58146	Norway-gardens and grass fields	2012	slugs (<i>A. vulgaris</i>)	ST120	NO-OTH-O-19
VI 58148	Norway-gardens and grass fields	2012	slugs (<i>A. vulgaris</i>)	ST91	NO-OTH-O-20
VI 58149	Norway-gardens and grass fields	2012	slugs (<i>A. vulgaris</i>)	ST18	NO-OTH-O-21

VI 58150	Norway-gardens and grass fields	2012	slugs (<i>A. vulgaris</i>)	ST1	NO-OTH-O-22
VI 58151	Norway-gardens and grass fields	2012	slugs (<i>A. vulgaris</i>)	ST1	NO-OTH-O-23
VI 58152	Norway-gardens and grass fields	2012	slugs (<i>A. vulgaris</i>)	ST91	NO-OTH-O-24
VI 58153	Norway-gardens and grass fields	2012	slugs (<i>A. vulgaris</i>)	ST91	NO-OTH-O-25
VI 58154	Norway-gardens and grass fields	2012	slugs (<i>A. vulgaris</i>)	ST17	NO-OTH-O-26
VI 58156	Norway-gardens and grass fields	2012	slugs (<i>A. vulgaris</i>)	ST403	NO-OTH-O-27
VI60966	Hunted animals, nature in Norway	2017	venision feces		NO-DEE-FE-1
VI60967	Hunted animals, nature in Norway	2017	venision feces		NO-DEE-FE-2
VI60968	Hunted animals, nature in Norway	2017	venision feces		NO-DEE-FE-3

3. Strains from ANSES

Cle anses	Info-epidemi_access	001_Country	NumOri
16SEL558LM	Cerveau de mouton	Slovénie	L829
16SEL533LM	Cerveau de renard	Slovénie	L774
16SEL561LM	cerveau bétail	Slovénie	L837
16SEL537LM	cerveau bétail	Slovénie	L781
16SEL560LM	cerveau de mouton	Slovénie	L834
16SEL540LM	Cerveau de mouton	Slovénie	L799
16SEL559LM	cerveau de chèvre	Slovénie	L831
16SEL556LM	foie de cerf	Slovénie	L816
16SEL543LM	Cerveau de mouton	Slovénie	L802
16SEL542LM	Cerveau de mouton	Slovénie	L801
16SEL534LM	Cerveau de renard	Slovénie	L775
16SEL535LM	Cerveau de renard	Slovénie	L777
16SEL539LM	cerveau bétail	Slovénie	L794
16SEL547LM	Cerveau de renard	Slovénie	L807
16SEL557LM	cerveau bétail	Slovénie	L817
16SEL562LM	cerveau cheval	Slovénie	L446
16SEL517LM	bovin ferme	Slovénie	L364
16SEL512LM	mouton	Slovénie	L209
16SEL516LM	bovin ferme	Slovénie	L363
16SEL518LM	bovin ferme	Slovénie	L567
16SEL525LM	Lait vache échantillon clinique	Slovénie	L635
16SEL528LM	Lait vache échantillon clinique	Slovénie	L638
16SEL529LM	chèvre	Slovénie	L675
16SEL530LM	cerveau de renard	Slovénie	L745
16SEL532LM	cerveau de renard	Slovénie	L750
16SEL544LM	Cerveau de mouton	Slovénie	L804
17SEL378LM	Slovenia SI01 Animal Animal health Brain Sheep	Slovenia	L124
17SEL384LM	Slovenia SI01 Animal Animal health Brain Goat	Slovenia	L313
16SEL517LM	bovin ferme	Slovenia	L364
17SEL388LM	Slovenia SI01 Animal Animal health Brain Goat	Slovenia	L666
17SEL389LM	Slovenia SI01 Animal Animal health Other Goat	Slovenia	L673
16SEL533LM	Cerveau de renard	Slovenia	L774
16SEL567LM	Placenta	Ille et Vilaine/Bretagne	10/7646

16SEL587LM	Placenta avortement	Ille et Vilaine/Bretagne	11/6006
16SEL575LM	Placenta avortement	Ille et Vilaine/Bretagne	10/16964
16SEL574LM	Placenta avortement	Ille et Vilaine/Bretagne	10/14551
16SEL697LM	estomac Avortement	Ille et Vilaine/Bretagne	13/26717
16SEL656LM	Placenta Avortemennt	Ille et Vilaine/Bretagne	12/16644
16SEL648LM	Placenta Avortemennt	Ille et Vilaine/Bretagne	12/12975
16SEL716LM	Placenta Avortement	Ille et Vilaine/Bretagne	14/15859
16SEL694LM	Placenta Avortement	Ille et Vilaine/Bretagne	13/15567
16SEL573LM	Placenta avortement	Ille et Vilaine/Bretagne	10/14041
16SEL588LM	encéphale avortement	Ille et Vilaine/Bretagne	11/7205
16SEL689LM	Placenta Avortement	Ille et Vilaine/Bretagne	13/6731
16SEL681LM	Placenta Avortement	Ille et Vilaine/Bretagne	13/2051
16SEL634LM	Placenta Avortemennt	Ille et Vilaine/Bretagne	11/16463
16SEL578LM	Placenta avortement	Ille et Vilaine/Bretagne	10/23530
16SEL572LM	Estomac avortement	Ille et Vilaine/Bretagne	10/11192
16SEL566LM	encéphale avortement	Ille et Vilaine/Bretagne	09/24400
16SEL710LM	Estomac Avortement	Ille et Vilaine/Bretagne	15/14217
16SEL692LM	Placenta Avortement	Ille et Vilaine/Bretagne	13/12752
16SEL667LM	placenta Avortement	Ille et Vilaine/Bretagne	12/25731
16SEL662LM	Placenta Avortement	Ille et Vilaine/Bretagne	12/17516
16SEL649LM	Lait Mammite	Ille et Vilaine/Bretagne	12/12971
16SEL571LM	Placenta avortement	Ille et Vilaine/Bretagne	10/10731
16SEL639LM	foie/rate Septicémie	Ille et Vilaine/Bretagne	11/25198
16SEL585LM	Placenta avortement	Ille et Vilaine/Bretagne	11/5470
16SEL638LM	encephale Avortemennt	Ille et Vilaine/Bretagne	11/21955
16SEL651LM	Placenta Avortemennt	Ille et Vilaine/Bretagne	12/14938
16SEL590LM	Placenta avortement	Ille et Vilaine/Bretagne	11/9376
16SEL622LM	litière	Allemagne	1259
16SEL617LM	toison	Allemagne	413
16SEL614LM	sol (abattoir)	Allemagne	357